

Mathematical modeling of chemical reaction on the onset of modulated thermo-solutal convection in a porous layer

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Abstract : The onset of thermo-solutal convection in a fluid-saturated porous layer is studied when the chemical equilibrium on the bounding surfaces and the solubility of the dissolved components depend on temperature. Sinusoidal vertical vibrations to the system are assumed to affect a time-dependent gravitational field for the onset of natural convection. A linear stability analysis is performed to obtain the Rayleigh number as a function of system parameters. The effect of chemical reaction parameter (Damköhler number) on Rayleigh number is depicted graphically and is discussed in detail.

Keywords : Double-diffusive convection, porous layer, gravity modulation, Damköhler number, chemical reaction.

Introduction

The problem of natural convection induced by the temperature as well as the concentration difference, viz. double-diffusive convection (DDC), has been of particular interest for researchers in recent past not only due to its challenging mathematical treatment but also due to its various practical applications in many branches of engineering such as chemical engineering, food processing and geothermal engineering etc. Nield was the first to give the mathematical treatment of the DDC in porous media (Nield (1968)). DDC under various physical and boundary conditions has been reported by Ingham and Pop (1998, 2005), Vafai (2000, 2005) and Nield and Bejan (2013).

In various chemical engineering processes and other industrial problems, such as manufacturing of ceramics or glassware, polymer production, food processing etc., we may come across the vital effect of reacting matters (fluids). The investigations related to the effect of chemical reaction on double-diffusive convection are due to Steinberg and Brand (1983, 1984), Pritchard and Richardson (2007), Wang and Tan (2009) and Malashetty and Biradar (2011). These studies report the characteristics of the convective flow and the effect of chemical reaction on the flow mechanism. A through survey on the literature shows that regulating the convective flow in the

case of chemical reaction need more attention. In the present work we address the problem of stability of natural convection in a Newtonian fluid-saturated porous layer under the combined effect of chemical reaction and gravity modulation.

Mathematical formulation :

The physical system consists of a horizontal infinitely extended Newtonian fluid-saturated porous layer heated and salted from below. The layer is confined between two parallel planes $z = 0$ and $z = d$ as shown in Fig. 1. Constant temperature and salinity gradient throughout the

Fig. 1. Schematic of the problem.

layer are maintained. In addition to this, the system is assumed to undergo vertical vibrations that lead to time-varying gravitational acceleration.

The physical system described above can be modeled using the equations :

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{q} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\rho_0}{\delta} \frac{\partial \vec{q}}{\partial t} + \nabla P + \frac{\mu}{K} \vec{q} - \rho \vec{g} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$(\rho c)_m \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + (\rho c)_f + (\vec{q} \cdot \nabla)T = (\rho c)_m \nabla \cdot (K_T \nabla T) \quad (3)$$

$$\delta \frac{\partial S}{\partial t} + (\vec{q} \cdot \nabla)S = \delta K_s \nabla^2 S + K (S_{eq}(T) - S) \quad (4)$$

$$\rho = \rho_0 [1 - \beta_T (T - T_0) + \beta_S (S - S_0)] \quad (5)$$

where \vec{q} is the velocity, ρ and μ represent density and viscosity of the fluid respectively. δ is the porosity and K is the permeability of the medium. The acceleration due to gravity is g , T is the temperature and S is the solute concentration. We have used K_T and K_S to denote the thermal conductivity and solute conductivity respectively. It is worth to note that the chemical reaction assumed here is of first order. To make the problem mathematically tractable, we assumed that the system equilibrium solute concentration as linear functions of temperature that can be written as

$$S_{eq}(t) = S_0 + \phi (T - T_0), \phi > 0 \quad (6)$$

The vertical vibrations are assumed to vary the gravitational field in the form :

$$\vec{g} = -g_0 (1 + \epsilon \cos \omega t) \quad (7)$$

The non-dimensional form of the above equations are (see Malashetty and Biradar (2011)) :

$$\left[\frac{1}{Va} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + 1 \right] \nabla^2 W - Ra_T F(t) \nabla_1^2 T + Ra_S F(t) \nabla_1^2 S = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \lambda (\vec{q} \cdot \nabla)T - \lambda W = \nabla^2 T \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} + (\vec{q} \cdot \nabla)S - W = \frac{1}{Le} \nabla^2 S + \chi(T - S) \quad (10)$$

To perform a linear stability analysis the non linear term in the above equations are omitted and the following normal mode solutions are considered :

$$\begin{bmatrix} W(x, y, z, t) \\ T(x, y, z, t) \\ S(x, y, z, t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} W(z, t) \\ \theta(z, t) \\ S(z, t) \end{bmatrix} \exp [i(lx + my)] \quad (11)$$

Hence the non-dimensional equations transformed to the form :

$$\left[\frac{1}{Va} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + 1 \right] (D^2 - K^2)W + Ra_T F(t) K^2 T - Ra_S F(t) K^2 S = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} - \lambda W = (D^2 - K^2)\theta \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} - W = \frac{1}{Le} (D^2 - K^2)S + \chi(T - S) \quad (14)$$

We use the following perturbation expansions for the physical quantities :

$$W(z, t) = W_s^{(0)}(z) + \frac{\epsilon}{2} [\psi_1(z) e^{i\omega t} + \bar{\psi}_1(z) e^{-i\omega t}] + \epsilon^2 W_s^{(2)}(z) \quad (15)$$

$$\theta(z, t) = \theta_s^{(0)}(z) + \frac{\epsilon}{2} [\theta_1(z) e^{i\omega t} + \bar{\theta}_1(z) e^{-i\omega t}] + \epsilon^2 D_s^{(2)}(z) \quad (16)$$

$$S(z, t) = S_s^{(0)}(z) + \frac{\epsilon}{2} [S_1(z) e^{i\omega t} + \bar{S}_1(z) e^{-i\omega t}] + \epsilon^2 D_s^{(2)}(z) \quad (17)$$

$$Ra_T = Ra_0 + \epsilon^2 Ra_2 + \dots \quad (18)$$

Substituting these in the above equations we get systems of various orders. At zero-th order we get

$$\begin{bmatrix} D^2 - K^2 & Ra_T K^2 & -Ra_S K^2 \\ \lambda & D^2 - K^2 & 0 \\ 1 & \chi & \frac{1}{Le} (D^2 - K^2) - \chi \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} W_s^{(0)} \\ \theta_s^{(0)} \\ S_s^{(0)} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

The boundary conditions are

$$W_s^{(0)} = \theta_s^{(0)} = S_s^{(0)} = 0 \text{ at } z = 0, 1 \quad (20)$$

For non-trivial solutions we get :

$$Ra_T = \frac{(\pi^2 + K^2)^2}{K^2} + Ra_s Le \left(\frac{\pi^2 + K^2 + \lambda\chi}{\pi^2 + K^2 + Le\chi} \right) \quad (21)$$

First order system is

$$\left[\frac{i\omega}{Va} + 1 \right] (D^2 - K^2)W_1(z) + Ra_0 K^2 \theta_1(z) - Ra_s K^2 S_1(z) = Ra_s K^2 \cos \omega t S_0 + Ra_0 K^2 \cos \omega t \theta_0 \quad (22)$$

$$(D^2 - K^2 - i\omega)\theta_1 = -\lambda\omega_1 \quad (23)$$

$$\left[\frac{1}{Le}(D^2 - K^2) - (\chi + i\omega) \right] S_1 = -W_1 - \chi T_1 \quad (24)$$

And the second order system is exactly the same as zero-th order system except the non-homogeneous terms for the three equation given by :

$$R_1 = -Ra_0 K^2 (\theta_1 + \bar{\theta}_1) \frac{1}{4} - Ra_2 K^2 \theta_0 + Ra_s K^2 (S_1 + \bar{S}_1) \frac{1}{4}, R_2 = 0, \text{ and } R_3 = 0 \quad (25)$$

Applying solvability condition (Suthar *et al.* (2013)) on this second order system, we get

$$Ra_2 = -Ra_0 \int_0^1 \frac{(\theta_1 + \bar{\theta}_1)}{2} \theta_0 dz + Ra_s K^2 \int_0^1 \frac{(S_1 + \bar{S}_1)}{2} \theta_0 dz \quad (26)$$

Results and discussion

The combined effect of time-dependent gravitational field and chemical reaction on the onset of double-diffusive convection has been studied by performing a linear stability analysis. The criteria for the onset of convection viz. Rayleigh number has been calculated as a function of various system parameters and the influence of various parameters is depicted in the Figs. 2-4. As reported in earlier studies concerning the effect of gravity modulation on the onset of thermal convection that at low frequencies the gravity modulation is destabilizing ($Ra_2 <$

0) whereas for moderate and large values of modulation frequency the system gets stabilized ($Ra_2 > 0$). The same can be observed in the Figs. 2-4. Moreover it can also be observed that at very high frequencies the effect of modulation disappears.

Now we proceed to discuss the effect of various parameters. Fig. 2 depicts the vital effect of Damköhler number on the correction in the critical Rayleigh number. It can be observed that its effect is to stabilize the system except for some small and moderate values of modulation frequencies. It is also interesting to note that the maximum value of Ra_2 is for approximately same value ($\omega = 7$) of the modulation frequency and thus the system can be most stabilized by applying a gravity modulation of this frequency with a specific Damköhler number.

In Fig. 3 we report the effect of solute Rayleigh num-

Fig. 2. Effect of χ on Ra_2 .

Fig. 3. Effect of Ra_s on Ra_2 .

ber on Ra_2 . The stabilizing effect of Ra_s can be readily observed from the Figure. The higher solute Rayleigh number represents higher values of δ_s which means that the fluid near the lower wall will be more dense due to concentration difference and thus the onset of convection will be delayed. Fig. 4 represents the effect of porous parameter Λ which is opposite to the effect of Damhölkar

Fig. 4. Effect of Λ on Ra_2 .

number. That means an increase in Λ will destabilize the system except for a certain range of values of modulation frequency.

Conclusion

The present model envisages the effect of chemical reaction on the onset of modulated thermo-solutal con-

vection in a porous layer. It leads to the conclusion that the effect of chemical reaction, which is characterized by the Damhölkar number, on the correction Rayleigh number is to stabilize the system for all but a set of values of the frequency of gravity modulation. Under the effect of gravity modulation the onset of convection can be advanced or delayed by proper tuning of the modulation frequency. The effect of solutal Rayleigh number is to stabilize the system under the influence of gravity modulation and chemical reaction.

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